

SOCIO-CULTURAL ACTIVITY: PRINCIPLES, TASKS AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses about basic principles, tasks and characteristics of socio-cultural activities which are of particular importance in society today. Social and cultural activities are aimed at creating conditions for people to realize their talents and abilities, to have a good rest, to have creative leisure, and to create a comfortable cultural environment for the whole country.

Keywords: *pedagogical activity, socio-cultural activity, principles of socio-cultural activity, social and cultural experiences, organizational and pedagogical features.*

In our country, the place and role of socio-cultural activity in the formation of a well-rounded person is of special importance in educating representatives of different classes of the population in artistic, aesthetic, moral, socio-political directions, increasing the spiritual and creative activity of people.

The history of socio-cultural activity is ancient. Its roots go back to the times of the first unifications of mankind. The first forms of unification are interpreted in scientific literature as having formed in the Stone, Bronze and Iron Ages. During this period, the cultural socialization of people arose from the need to ensure life and determine its stable duration. In order to ensure the material aspects of life, people taught each other to hunt, fish, grow plants, attract the opposite sex through various games and exercises. Learning was continuous, uninterrupted. Continuity and consistency of teaching determined the formation of education as a separate area. Thus, it can be said that socio-cultural activity is the basis of education [2].

Pedagogical foundations of socio-cultural activity is a set of knowledge that reveals the characteristics of the processes of learning, education and development of people in the course of socio-cultural activity. Education in the process of socio-cultural activity is a purposeful activity organized for the dissemination of general, cultural and special knowledge, development of skills and abilities necessary for life and successful work. Enrichment with new knowledge, skills and abilities is carried out in special classes, during exercises, and independently on the example of cultural

and artistic images. Such an event is characterized by the following features: expediency, versatility, active interaction, creative orientation, orientation from simple to complex, high motivation of participants.

Independence also made it possible to form the most general rules - principles, which express the nature of social and cultural activities of the social and cultural institutions operating in our republic and determine its direction, content and forms.

The specific principles of socio-cultural activity are considered the main source of guidance in the organization of socio-cultural activity, and they consist of the following [2]:

- vitality;
- publicness;
- voluntariness;
- scientificity.

The coordination of the practice of continuous development of our independent state with the vital requirements, explaining the nature of the tasks facing people, educating them in the spirit of strengthening independence and realizing their historical role in building a great future state indicates the vitality of social and cultural activities.

The principle of vitality of socio-cultural activity includes the features of accuracy and goal orientation. This means that every event in a cultural institution should have a specific character and a specific purpose in relation to the requirements of the independence period. It encourages the formation of a well-developed personality with all its nature and content, gives a person the opportunity to show his abilities and talents, and adds color to his life.

The public principle of socio-cultural activity fulfills a number of socially important tasks. That is, it develops social and cultural creativity and social activity of the public, organizes public communication and forms public opinion based on this.

The peculiarity of the principle of publicness from the point of view of impact on the individual is that everyone can participate in socio-cultural events not only as a spectator or observer, but as an active participant of the happening events, a person expressing his views. At the same time, the principle of publicness allows a person to express himself socially.

Social and cultural institutions attract people to social and creative activity on a voluntary basis, in the spirit of constant respect and trust. Social and cultural activities always work on the basis of voluntary principles. If human activity in work teams is sometimes determined for purely material reasons, in socio-cultural activity, first of all, interest in the content of the activity is in the main place. In other words, the community of socio-cultural institution gives freedom to manifest and develop the

spiritual and creative abilities of an individual. Voluntariness reflects the ability to freely choose one of the many types of activities offered by social and cultural institutions, and represents the ability of a person to determine the content of his social and cultural activities in his free time.

The scientific principle is manifested in a number of signs. Among them, the first place can be allocated to the sign of objectivity. Social and cultural activities should have an educational effect. Taking into account the real possibilities for such influence, it is necessary to rationally use the objective laws of the development of society and individual.

Science makes it possible to reveal events, facts and their essence, to determine the real picture of social life and its development processes, and the level of social development. It is an important task of socio-cultural activity to prevent the accidental impact of the perception of reality and to create a truly scientific vision of the world around us. The scientific principle contributes to strengthening the formation of a person's worldview.

The principles of socio-cultural activity do not exist separately from each other, on the contrary, they form a whole system and represent an integral part of a single process in the socio-cultural activity of the masses. The absence of any one of these principles leads to a violation of the overall integrity.

Speaking about socio-cultural activity, Professor V.E.Triodin emphasized that, by its essence, "man has a creative nature, and it is aimed at revealing his unique potential in every way, improving it. In this sense, socio-cultural activity is educational activity, and accordingly, the theory of this process is pedagogy by definition [1].

T.A. Kemerova wrote in the textbook "Theory of Socio-Cultural Activity": "Today, socio-cultural activity is considered as a field of socio-cultural practice and an independent field of cultural knowledge" [3]. Moreover, if we fully agree with the first part, we do not fully accept the second - in order to be a "field of knowledge", the activity must be understood at a scientific level, that is, it becomes a theory. Therefore, in the quoted passage, we are talking about two different and non-accidental levels of attribute of the concept - ontological and epistemological.

The organizational-pedagogical characteristics of the socio-cultural activities of the master's students include several important aspects. These features aim to provide students with opportunities to participate in social and cultural experiences that complement their academic education and contribute to their overall personal and professional development. Here we will show some of the main organizational and pedagogical features [6]:

Fig. 1. Organizational and pedagogical features of socio-cultural activities

By introducing these organizational-pedagogical features into socio-cultural activities, master's students become mature professionals. They will also have access to a holistic learning experience that goes beyond academics and contributes to their personal growth, intercultural competence and readiness for professional life.

Socio-cultural activity is a type of pedagogical activity, based on pedagogical technologies with general characteristics and organizational characteristics of pedagogical activity, it is a person as a cultural subject with the functional goals of organizational and management, information and education, recreation and health, entertainment and hedonism, animation, rehabilitation. dialectically combines the specific features of upbringing.

So, socio-cultural activity gives a person the opportunity to develop as a person, self-organization and personal development skills and teaches them to use them creatively.

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